

VERITY Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science

ENGAGING THE PUBLIC IN SCIENTIFIC PROCESSES

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the Public in
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Processes

VERITY research demonstrates that **involving the public in scientific processes** strengthens trust in science by promoting transparency and mutual understanding between researchers and society. Rather than treating the public as passive recipients of science communication, meaningful engagement positions them as active contributors to research design and implementation. This approach enhances the accountability of scientific methods and ensures that research aligns with societal needs. By encouraging citizen participation, the recommendations in this category aim to demystify complex scientific concepts, foster critical engagement with evidence-based information, and address scepticism by integrating diverse perspectives, ultimately **cultivating a shared sense of ownership over scientific progress.**

How to support the public's involvement in scientific processes?

ENGAGING THE PUBLIC IN SCIENTIFIC PROCESSES:

Building Frameworks for Sustainable Engagement

- Shift from one-way deficit models of science communication towards relational approaches that foster mutual trust through dialogue and meaningful engagement.
- Break silos between mainstream research and citizen engagement by integrating the public as active contributors to research processes.
- Build inclusive engagement platforms such as citizen assemblies and participatory initiatives at all levels (the EU, national, and local) that connect researchers, citizens, policymakers, civil society, businesses, and the media.

Recognising, Funding, and Rewarding Public Engagement

- Reward scientists and stakeholders for public engagement through dedicated funding schemes and inclusion in academic evaluation metrics.

- Adjust funding frameworks to accommodate the longer timelines and additional resources required for meaningful citizen engagement.
- Establish fair compensation mechanisms for citizen contributions and recognise public engagement as integral to research impact.
- Advocate for inclusive authorship policies in academic publishing to credit citizen contributions.

Tailored Approaches

- Make scientific processes more inclusive by actively involving marginalised and underrepresented groups (particularly those with lower educational attainment, economically vulnerable individuals, and older adults), using approaches tailored to socio-demographic factors, belief profiles, and community-specific needs.
- Identify the diverse characteristics and needs of different communities through consultative social scientific methods such as interviews and focus groups, which will provide insights for designing and implementing tailored strategies for public engagement.

Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing

- Create communities of practice that bring together researchers and citizens to share knowledge, co-develop quality standards, and identify best practices for public engagement, supported by clear guidelines, practical training, and realistic planning tools.
- Encourage scientists to incorporate local knowledge and address community-specific needs.
- Cultivate public interest in science through hands-on activities, interactive tools, and citizen co-creation projects.
- Organise initiatives like Open Science Days to disseminate research results and gather public input to inform policymaking and research.

Fostering Critical Thinking

- Promote critical thinking, rather than blind trust, to build resilience against mis/disinformation and mistrust.

- Combat mis/disinformation by actively engaging with the public, collaborating with civil society, and disseminating research results.

Monitoring and Sustainability

- Implement clear and consistent feedback mechanisms to ensure participants remain informed and engaged throughout and beyond the research process.
- Adapt feedback mechanisms to specific challenges of research in fragile contexts (e.g. high-risk regions or socio-economically vulnerable settings).

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VERITY Recommendations on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/16975899>

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